

Informing Sustainable Energy Policy in Developing Countries: An Assessment of Decarbonization Pathways in Colombia Using Open Energy System Optimization Modelling

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Supplementary information

APPENDIX A. Calibration results

Since ESOMs cannot be properly validated (Pfenninger et al., 2014), the models are calibrated by checking the consistency of the model results with respect to a past or present state using a reference year (Limpens et al., 2020). In our case, the calibration year is 2021. We compared the model results with the produced energy reported by the Colombian energy balance in 2021 (UPME, 2022b), and we obtained a relative error of 1.5% (Figure 1). The main differences in energy balance are due to unbalance of bioethanol-gasoline and biodiesel-diesel, as the model assumes a constant blending percentage (8% for bioethanol and 10% for biodiesel), while the country has different percentages depending on the region.

Figure 1. Model results versus real produced energy in 2021

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APPENDIX B. Sectoral results

B.1. Transport sector

Road transport depends almost fully on internal combustion engine vehicles (ICE), with gasoline and diesel as main fuels. For private passenger transport, the electrification of the vehicle fleet is the strategy of decarbonization for all the groups of technologies. From 2022 to 2040, there is a continuous penetration of BEV and PHEV, replacing ICE vehicles to achieve a 100% electrified fleet after 2040 in the FWD and motorcycle groups, as illustrated in Figure 2. In the case of light-duty vehicles, the electrification is slower and occurs in the 2040's in the ADPS scenario. For the DSP scenario, the negative emissions from BECCS enable to maintain some fossil fuel uses, such as the gasoline vehicles in the light-duty vehicles segment. FCEV are not competitive in any segment of private passenger transport.

Figure 2. Distribution of private passenger road transport demand by type

In the public road passenger sector, electric vehicles represent the alternative to decarbonize the final services. Figure 3 shows that taxis are fully electrified by 2040's while microbuses and buses would take some time more towards 2045. For taxi vehicles, natural gas, diesel, and gasoline are progressively replaced by electricity as fuel in the decarbonization scenarios. In the DPS scenario, ICE microbuses keep a 40% share beyond 2030 and face a continuous decrease from 2035 to 2050. In the case of buses, FCEV supports around 10% of transport demand by 2050 in the DPS and ADPS scenarios. The use of hydrogen as transport fuel is solely observed in the buses segment for the scenarios modelled.

Figure 3. Distribution of public road passenger transport demand by type

Cargo transport is one of the more challenging sectors to be decarbonized due to the energy requirements in terms of long distances and transported weights. Under the assumption of electric trucks and semi-trailer trucks available from 2030, the results show the electrification of both demands by 2050, as illustrated in Figure 4. Trucks are electrified more quickly targeting 2040 as final year. Semi-trailer trucks exhibit a similar behavior over 2045. Fossil fuels are not competitive due to emission constraints and hydrogen seems not be enough cost-effective to be included as a fuel for future cargo transport.

Figure 4. Distribution of road cargo transport demand by type

Apart from contributing to GHG emissions reduction, the electrified fleet improves the efficiency of the sector. In the BAU scenario, the energy consumption for transport reaches 1492 PJ by 2050, and the decarbonization pathways even reduce their energy use with respect to 2021, achieving 483.7 PJ in the DPS scenario and 422.2 PJ in the ADPS scenario. Figure 5 presents the comparison of efficiency between scenarios and sectors. The efficiency of passenger transport grows from 1.7 Gpkm/PJ in the BAU scenario to 5.2 Gpkm/PJ in the DPS scenario and 6.4 Gpkm/PJ in the ADPS scenario by 2050. Regarding the cargo transport, the efficiency also skyrockets passing from 0.7 Gtkm/PJ in the BAU scenario to 7.2 Gtkm/PJ in both DPS and ADPS scenarios by 2050.

Figure 5. Comparison of efficiency results by scenario and sector

B.2. Industry sector

Direct heat demand is mainly provided by natural gas and coal in the BAU scenario as shown in Figure 6. In the DPS scenario, biomass and natural gas furnaces coupled with CCS play a key role to mitigate GHG emissions, representing 87% of total direct heat demand by 2050. Regarding the ADPS scenario, hydrogen and electricity become the options to decarbonize the direct heat demand by 2050. Biomass remains relevant for direct heat supply with a 13% share in both DPS and ADPS scenarios. Coal reduces its share to zero by 2050 in both decarbonization pathways and coal furnaces with CCS are not used under any condition modelled. The consumption of energy for direct heat is 325.9 PJ by 2050 in the BAU scenario, against 367.5 PJ in the DPS scenario, an increase derived from the deployment of CCS technologies that are less efficient. On the contrary, the ADPS scenario uses 291 PJ for direct heat representing an improvement of 7% in efficiency.

With respect to indirect heat demand, a combination of biomass, coal, natural and electric boilers are used to satisfy the energy needs in the BAU scenario. CCS technologies along with natural gas boilers substitute other alternatives except for biomass boilers, and reach 85% of indirect heat supply by 2050 in the DPS scenario. Without CCS options, hydrogen-fueled boilers lead the provision of indirect heat with 50% by 2050 and followed by biomass with 41% in the ADPS scenario. In terms of energy consumption, the DPS scenario requires 320.3 PJ and the APDS uses almost the half with 158.2 PJ, demonstrating the inefficiency of CCS technologies. Figure 5 corroborates this fact indicating that the whole efficiency of industry sector declines by 1.7% by 2050 in the DPS scenario and increases by 7.4% in the ADPS scenario.

Figure 6. Distribution of industry demand by demand type

B.3. Residential sector

In the residential sector, the principal use of energy is cooking, which is supplied by natural gas and LPG in the BAU scenario. The decarbonization of this sector is based on electrifying the cooking services. Figure 7 depicts the evolution of electrification of cooking by 2045 in both DPS and ADPS scenarios. In the case of water heating, the availability of natural gas resources during the 2040's enables a cost-optimal use in water heating for the DPS and ADPS scenarios. The DPS scenario suggests replacing all electric heaters by natural gas heaters to provide hot water by 2050. Regarding other appliances (e.g., refrigerators, lightening, washers), the transformation of the sector is propelled

by the change of low-efficiency equipment by high-efficiency utilities. The results expected a full conversion by 2035. The electrification and use of more efficient appliances increase the efficiency of the sector moving from 32% in the BAU scenario to 51% in the DPS and ADPS scenarios by 2050.

Figure 7. Distribution of residential demand by demand type

B.4. Commercial and public sector

Natural gas and LPG dominate the demand supply of cooking in the commercial and public sector in the BAU scenario, as shown in Figure 8. The DPS scenario displays an electrification of cooking between 2022 and 2035, and then there is a deployment of natural gas stoves to reach 88% of total demand by 2050. In the case of the ADPS scenario, the electrification is the optimal solution for cooking, and it replaces all natural gas and LPG stoves by 2050. Regarding the indirect heat demand, natural gas boilers lead the 100% of use in both BAU and DPS scenarios by 2050. However, the ADPS scenario reduces the use of natural gas and accomplishes a full electrified system for indirect heat by 2050. The DPS scenario shows the feasibility of including natural gas as energy carrier when there is a wider carbon budget due to negative emissions contribution. For the remainder electric services (i.e., refrigeration, lightening, air conditioning and electronics), the conversion from low-efficiency utilities to high-efficiency ones is achieved by 2030. As illustrated in Figure 5, the sector efficiency is 25% in the BAU scenario, and grows to 35% in the DPS scenario and 39% in the ADPS scenario. Electrification demonstrates to be more efficient measured compared to natural gas use, although investment costs are higher.

Figure 8. Distribution of commercial and public demand by demand type